

A Pseudonymisation-by-Design Procedure for Classroom Observations Based on a Seating Plan

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Authors: Kenneth Hemmerechts and Nohemi Jocabeth Echeverria Vicente

Affiliation: Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB)

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Abstract

This methodological note outlines a pseudonymisation-by-design procedure for video-based and in-person classroom observations in the Horizon Europe project, [Gender Empowerment Through Politics in the Classroom](#) (G-EPIC). Having been successfully implemented in a cross-national study conducted as part of Work Package 3, this approach enables the systematic observation and analysis of classroom interactions while safeguarding participant identities from the outset. Embedding safeguards directly into the research design rather than applying them post hoc ensures privacy by design and minimises the processing of personal data, which is critical when working with vulnerable participants, such as minors, in educational settings. The procedure is based on spatial seating plans with numeric identifiers, enabling researchers to track participation patterns and link them to other forms of data collection without collecting names or other direct identifiers. This method is particularly well-suited to qualitative and mixed-methods studies involving video recordings or in-person classroom observations, and it supports full compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and Horizon Europe ethics requirements.

Aims and scope

Observational research in educational settings, whether based on video recordings or in-person observations, poses significant ethical challenges, particularly when involving minors. Researchers are confronted with the challenge of ensuring anonymity in accordance with the stipulations set out by prevailing data protection frameworks, such as the European Union General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). While the focus is primarily on ensuring pseudonymisation procedures after data collection, this framework emphasises the principle of 'data protection by design' to guarantee the confidentiality of study participants before data collection and as an integral part of the research design.

One implication of the 'privacy by design' principle is the need to minimise data collection to the research's objectives. Additionally, data must be pseudonymised, which involves replacing personally identifiable material with artificial identifiers. Consequently, researchers must devise novel methodologies to ensure pseudonymisation and the collection of only the necessary information from the outset.

The **pseudonymised classroom seating plan procedure** adopts this ex-ante logic by embedding pseudonymisation at the point of data generation which enables the systematic analysis of classroom interactions while avoiding the use of unnecessary identifiable personal data, such as names, in observation and coding. This procedure is intended to ensure compliance with ethical and legal standards (including GDPR) and to support cross-national comparability of classroom-based research. The method can be applied to classroom video-based and in-person observations, as well as interaction analysis (for example, participation/hand raising, interaction, and group dynamics) and gender and intersectional analysis in educational contexts.

The present procedure was originally developed and field-tested as part of the data collection of Work Package 3 of the G-EPIC project for video recordings and in-person observations in five countries: Belgium, the Czech Republic, Denmark, Germany and the United Kingdom. The empirical use of this method for the analysis of the link between hand-raising and social status in the Belgian sample is currently in preparation for a forthcoming journal article. Researchers using this methodological note are encouraged to check for the published version of the empirical study for further context on the results.

Conceptual Approach

The procedure is based on the **principle of pseudonymisation-by-design**, meaning that identity protection is embedded in the research design itself. Data is also structured so that any identifiable information not recorded initially is not required at the analysis stage. In this sense, *pseudonymisation is treated as an ex-ante process* rather than a subsequent transformation. Consequently, unlike post hoc anonymisation, no direct identifiers (e.g. names) are used in the analytical datasets, as the observations and coding rely exclusively on spatial identifiers based on the classroom seating plan (see Figure 1). This procedure aligns with the GDPR principles of data minimisation and data protection by design and by default, as set out in Article 25.

Description of the Method

To meet the objectives of Work Package 3, which aimed to assess classroom discussion dynamics, video recordings and/or in-person observations were conducted in classrooms. Pre- and post-test surveys, focus groups with students and interviews with teachers were also carried out. These methods enabled detailed documentation of interactions between students, between students and teachers, and between teachers and students, as well as data triangulation. We sought to link key demographic characteristics (e.g. gender, socioeconomic status and migration background) and other predictors of political interest and engagement to each participant observed in the classroom. This was done in order to develop hypotheses on predictors of classroom engagement and later use this information to inform the development of gender empowerment interventions aimed at boosting the political self-efficacy of girls and other disadvantaged students.

The pseudonymised classroom seating plan ensures that personal data is collected only to the extent necessary for the research goals and that pseudonymisation procedures are implemented as soon as possible. To fulfil the first requirement, the seating plan avoids recording students' names from the outset. Instead, we replaced identifiable personal data with numerical identifiers using the seating plan. The second requirement is met by using this fixed class seating plan to link the observations to individuals, pseudonymising the data by design.

The first phase of this process involves *creating a seating plan for the classroom*. Initially, the seating plan should be drawn up to match the classroom layout as closely as possible, including distinctive features such as the board, screen, closets, windows and doors. This will allow individuals to be placed in the correct spatial location. This can be reinforced by labelling the front and back of the classroom. The teacher's table and the arrangement of the students' seats should be recorded in numerical order (e.g. 1–20; see Figure 1 for an example), specifying whether they are arranged in rows or otherwise. Numbers will be assigned by researchers using a single logic. In the example presented, the numbers were assigned from left to right and from top to bottom of the figure. During the data collection phase, this information enables the accurate recording of classroom interactions. During the analysis phase, the classroom layout helps us to understand its impact on interactions between students and teachers, as well as on teaching methods.

Before the data collection phase begins, a schematic representation of the classroom should be created that accurately reflects the usual setup and incorporates the necessary contextual details into the coding of any observations. It is recommended that researchers visit the classroom beforehand to draw the layout and ask the teacher about the normal setup for a particular class. This will enable greater detail and accuracy to be recorded. They should also

ask whether students tend to work in groups, change seats or sit in the same place throughout the year. The extent to which the classroom seating plan procedure can be implemented as indicated here depends on these elements, as well as on whether adaptations are needed to follow students at different times. Please note that this procedure assumes relatively stable seating arrangements during the data collection phases. The fixed nature of the plan requires students to remain in their assigned positions throughout the observed sessions in order to maintain the integrity of the numeric identifiers.

At this stage, the classroom layout should be shared with the teacher to allow for modifications, and a definitive version should be agreed upon prior to data collection. One copy should be given to the teacher and another to the researchers. This final version will serve as a template for linking in-person observations to specific individuals during the data collection phase, and for video recordings during the analysis phase (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Example Classroom Seating Plan Template for Pseudonymised Observations.

Source: Developed by authors.

Following the creation of the seating plan, the second phase involves *generating the re-identification key*, which is a record linking the spatial numeric identifiers to the students' names. The researchers will not be involved in this process to avoid recording unnecessary personal data. In order to assign the correct numeric identifier to each student according to their usual seating position, the teacher's assistance will be required. The teacher's role is to write the name of each student on the classroom layout provided by the researchers, alongside the corresponding number. The aim is to replicate the usual classroom setup as closely as possible to ensure the smooth implementation of data collection. This will make data collection less intrusive for students, as it will not interfere with the way they usually follow lessons, unless there is a need to change this — for example, to implement specific didactic interventions.

During this phase, it is assumed that each student has a fixed position in the classroom and will be allocated a unique number on the seating plan by the teacher, based on their usual seat. This identifier cannot be changed at different stages of the data collection process to

ensure adequate linkage between observation periods and other data collection methods, such as surveys or focus groups, at earlier or later stages, and to triangulate information. This means that teachers need to ensure that students remain in the same position throughout the data collection process. Furthermore, to guarantee adequate linkage, it is important that students receive their corresponding number from the teacher, or that the teacher projects the visual diagram with numbers and names prior to the start of the data collection process, so that students can provide this information when requested, for example during pre-tests, post-tests or focus groups. We recommend not sharing the seating plan with students in physical or digital form. This is because sharing the diagram with students could result in the key being disseminated, which would make it more difficult to implement the later pseudonymisation steps. It is therefore crucial to communicate these instructions clearly to the teacher to ensure the procedure is implemented correctly.

Once the seating plan has been completed with the students' names and numeric identifiers, the teacher will retain the plan and be the only person with the key to link the students' names to their identifiers on the plan.

After data collection, the next steps in *producing pseudonymised datasets* in the third phase should consist of a multi-stage process:

1) Separating the personal data from the identifiers. Ensuring that only the teacher has the key effectively separates the personal data from the numerical identifiers, since the teacher will not have access to the completed surveys, field notes or observation data. Instead, they will have the number identifiers and student names. The researchers will have access to the collected data and the number identifiers, but not the students' names or the classroom plan. This enables the researchers to analyse the data without the students' names.

2) The collected personal data will be categorised into broad categories. For example, when recording country of origin in the pseudonymised dataset, regions or clusters of countries should be used instead of individual countries. Furthermore, research findings must be reported in summary or aggregate form to ensure no individual student can be identified through data triangulation.

3) Student and school identifiers should be randomised before sharing it with researchers outside of the research team. This will make it impossible to re-identify individual students or schools within the dataset, even when the key is compromised.

4) In alignment with the principle of storage limitation, the teacher should be requested to destroy the class seating plan approximately three months after the conclusion of the fieldwork. This timeframe should be agreed with the teacher in advance and incorporated into a data retention and disposal protocol, approved by the Data Protection Officer of the research institution.

During the fourth phase, data analysis, the seating plan can be used as a visual diagram to help researchers link the key demographic characteristics collected in the pre- and post-test questionnaires to the video recordings or observations, since no names are recorded. The spatial cues in the seating plan enable researchers to easily and accurately record different types of interaction, whether in situ or when revisiting the video recordings. For example, the seating plan and numeric identifiers can be used to easily record how many times a student speaks or is asked by the teacher.

Final remarks

This methodological note has detailed a pseudonymisation-by-design procedure to proactively ensure participants' privacy when using high-resolution observational methods linked or triangulated with other data forms. The note demonstrates how the method operationalises the Privacy by Design principle (Art. 25 GDPR) prior to data collection, meeting the dual requirements of data minimisation and rapid pseudonymisation by using a spatial mapping approach with classroom seating plans.

The efficacy of this approach relies on a seating plan that assigns spatial numeric identifiers to students instead of names on the seating plan, thereby minimising the collection of personal data while allowing for precise data linking across observations, surveys, and focus groups. This is further strengthened by the structural separation of identifiers between the teacher and the researchers from the outset. This ex-ante approach is superior to post-hoc anonymisation, as it mitigates the risk of accidental re-identification during the sensitive stages of video analysis and data transcription.

The successful implementation of this framework within the cross-national G-EPIC project demonstrates its methodological robustness and scalability. This standardised protocol can be applied to various school settings, complies with the highest level of data protection requirements, and can serve as a reference for future studies that seek to reconcile individual-level tracking with safeguarding privacy. Furthermore, this method emphasises the importance of safeguarding the privacy of vulnerable participants through rigorous design as part of conducting high-quality research in educational settings.